

Supplementary material for
**Time-aligned spatial upsampling
of spherical microphone array recordings**

Journal of the Audio Engineering Society (2024)
<https://doi.org/10.17743/jaes.2022.0166>

**Christoph Pörschmann¹, Tim Lübeck^{1,2},
and Johannes M. Arend³**

¹*Institute of Computer and Communication Technology,
TH Köln - University of Applied Sciences*

²*Audio Communication Group,
Technical University of Berlin*

²*Department of Information and Communications Engineering,
Aalto University*

christoph.poerschmann@th-koeln.de
tim.luebeck@th-koeln.de
johannes.arend@aalto.fi

Contents

1	Technical Evaluation - Additional Information	1
1.1	Simulated Plane Waves - $N = \{1,2,3\}$	1
1.2	Interaural coherence - three plane waves	5
2	Perceptual Evaluation - Additional Information	6
2.1	General Information	6
2.2	Statistical Results	9

1 Technical Evaluation - Additional Information

1.1 Simulated Plane Waves - $N = \{1,2,3\}$

We show the results of the technical evaluation for three simulated plane waves and sparse sampling grids of lower order than shown in the paper $N = \{1, 2, 3\}$. The energy distribution in the spherical harmonics domain is shown in Figure S1.

Figure S1: Energy distribution of reference, and of sparse and upsampled SH coefficients at $N = \{1, 2, 3\}$. The gray lines show the SH order below which 99% of the energy is contained. The top right plot summarizes the 99% energy curves for all conditions. Here, the black line indicates the $N = 44$ reference, the blue color indicates the SARITA conditions, and the different red tones the sparse conditions.

The magnitudes of the decomposed plane waves over frequency (x-axis) and azimuth (y-axis) for $N = \{1, 2, 3\}$ and for the reference at $N = 44$ are shown in Figure S2.

Figure S2: Plane wave magnitudes energy-normalized over frequency (1/12 octave smoothed) of the simulated SMAs with sampling grids of orders $N = \{1, 2, 3\}$ and the reference at $N = 44$.

We further examined the effects on binaural reproduction for $N = \{1, 2, 3\}$. The logarithmic differences $\Delta G(\omega)$ between the magnitude spectra of the binaural renderings to the reference are shown in Figure S3.

Figure S3: One-third octave smoothed magnitude differences $\Delta G(\omega)$ in dB (left ear) between the binaural reference signals B_{ref} and the sparse binaural signals $B_{N1/2/3}$ or the upsampled binaural signals $\hat{B}_{N1/2/3}$.

Fig. S4 shows the ITDs and ILDs as well as the differences of the ITDs and ILDs (Δ ITDs, Δ ILDs) compared to the reference, and just noticeable differences (JNDs) for ITDs.

Figure S4: ILDs and ITDs and their differences from the reference, shown as the dashed black curve, for a single impinging plane wave at $N = \{1, 2, 3\}$. The left plots show the values determined from the sparse array recordings, the right plots those from the array recordings upsampled with SARITA. In the difference plots, the gray regions show the JNDs.

Figure S5 shows the interaural coherence of the binaural signals for one impinging plane wave at $N = \{1, 2, 3\}$.

Figure S5: Interaural coherence for one impinging plane wave with sampling grids of orders $N = \{1, 2, 3\}$ and the reference at $N = 44$.

1.2 Interaural coherence - three plane waves

Figures S6 and S7 show the interaural coherence of the binaural signals for an incidence of three simulated plane waves. The sparse datasets in both plots at $N = \{1, 2, 3, 5, 7\}$ (left columns) are above the respective f_a affected by undersampling errors and show differences to the reference ($N = 44$). For the upsampled datasets (right column) the pattern can be regarded being closer to the reference.

Figure S6: Interaural coherence for three simulated plane waves with sampling grids of orders $N = \{3, 5, 7\}$ and the reference at $N = 44$

Figure S7: Interaural coherence for three simulated plane waves with sampling grids of orders $N = \{1, 2, 3\}$ and the reference at $N = 44$

2 Perceptual Evaluation - Additional Information

2.1 General Information

Table 1 and Table 2 give the descriptions of the SAQI attributes as they were described to the subjects. As the test was carried out with German-speaking subjects in this test, we used the descriptions from Table 2. Figure S8 shows the Graphical User Interface (GUI) as it was presented to the subjects during the experiment.

Table 1: English SAQI attributes and circumscription used in the listening experiment.

Perceptual quality	Circumscription	Scale and label
Difference	Existence of a noticeable difference	none - very large
Coloration	Timbral change	none – very large
Source position	Perceived position of the sound source	Unchanged - changed
Externalization	Some really Describes the distinctness with which a sound source is perceived within or outside the head regardless of their distance. Terminologically often enclosed between the phenomena of in-head localization and out-ofhead localization. Examples: Poorly/not externalized = perceived position of sound sources at diotic sound presentation via headphones, good/strongly externalized = perceived position of a natural source in reverberant environment and when allowing for movements of the listener	more internalized – more externalized
Source width	Perceived extent of a sound source in radial and horizontal direction	less wide - wider
Envelopment	Sensation of being spatially surrounded by the reverberation. With more pronounced envelopment of reverberation, it is increasingly difficult to assign a specific position, a limited extension or a preferred direction to the reverberation. Impressions of either low or high reverberation envelopment arise with either diotic or dichotic (i.e., uncorrelated) presentation of reverberant audio material.	less pronounced – more pronounced

Table 2: German SAQI attributes and circumscription used in the listening experiment.

Wahrnehmungsqualität	Beschreibung	Skalenpole
Unterschied	Existenz eines wahrnehmbaren Unterschieds.	gar keiner- sehr großer
Klangverfärbung	Klangliche Veränderungen	gar keine - große
Schallquell Position	Schallquellenpositionsänderung	unverändert- verändert
Externalisierungsgrad	Beschreibt die Deutlichkeit, mit der eine Schallquelle unabhängig von ihrer Distanz - innerhalb oder außerhalb des Kopfes wahrgenommen wird. Fachlich oft auch zwischen Phänomenen Im-Kopf-Lokalisation und Außer-Kopf-Lokalisation eingegrenzt. Beispiele: Schlecht/nicht externalisiert = wahrgenommener Schallquellenort bei diotischer Schallpräsentation per Kopfhörer; Gut/stark externalisiert = wahrgenommener Schallquellenort beim Hören einer natürlichen Schallquelle in nachhallbehafteter Umgebung unter Zulassen von Bewegungen des Hörers	internalisierter - externalisierter
Quellausdehnung	Veränderung der Quellbreite	weniger breit - breit
Nachhallumhüllung	Wahrnehmung des vom-Nachhall-räumlich-umhüllt-Seins. Bei hoher N. kann dem Nachhall nur schwer ein spezifischer Ort, eine begrenzte Ausdehnung oder eine Vorzugsrichtung zugewiesen werden. Eindrücke eher niedriger bzw. eher hoher N. entstehen z.B. bei diotisch vs. Dichotisch (z.B. dekorreliert) präsentiertem verhaltenen Material	schwächer ausgeprägt - stärker ausgeprägt

Figure S8: Graphical User Interface of the listening experiment.

2.2 Statistical Results

Table 3 shows the means, standard deviations (SD) and medians of the result of the SAQI test averaged over rooms and orders. Table 4 – Table 9 depict the result for the ANOVAs for each of the attributes tested in the SAQI experiment. In all tables we report Greenhouse-Geiser corrected p-values.

Table 3: Descriptive values of the results of the SAQI experiment.

Attribute	Sparse			SARITA		
	mean	SD	median	mean	SD	median
difference	1.33	0.89	1	0.72	0.85	1.0
coloration	1.3	0.9	1.2	0.42	0.67	0.1
source position	0.49	0.61	0.25	0.48	0.75	0.0
externalization	-0.31	0.87	0.0	-0.30	0.72	0.0
source width	-0.72	0.86	-0.9	0.08	0.76	0.0
envelopment	0.25	0.83	0	-0.11	0.56	0.0

Table 4: ANOVA for the attribute difference.

Effect	df_{num}	df_{den}	F	p	η_p^2	ϵ
room	1	9	19.76	< .001	.70	1.00
order	2	18	22.72	< .001	.72	0.83
method	1	9	26.01	< .001	.74	1.00
signal	1	9	13.08	< .001	.60	1.00
room \times order	2	18	0.27	.268	.14	0.96
room \times method	1	9	4.15	.072	.32	1.00
order \times method	2	18	2.28	.408	.08	0.54
room \times signal	1	9	2.49	.149	.22	1.00
order \times signal	2	18	3.74	.045	.29	0.97
method \times signal	1	9	3.08	.113	.25	1.00
room \times order \times method	2	18	3.80	.042	.30	1.00
room \times order \times signal	2	18	0.20	.782	.02	0.84
room \times method \times signal	1	9	0.12	.741	.01	1.00
order \times method \times signal	2	18	0.51	.560	.05	0.75
room \times order \times method \times signal	2	18	0.44	.626	.04	0.87

Table 5: ANOVA for the attribute coloration.

Effect	df_{num}	df_{den}	F	p	η_p^2	ϵ
room	1	9	57.80	< .001	.87	1.00
order	2	18	13.54	.002	.60	0.70
method	1	9	83.24	< .001	.90	1.00
signal	1	9	5.58	.042	.38	1.00
room \times order	2	18	0.55	.565	.06	0.87
room \times method	1	9	8.40	.018	.48	1.00
order \times method	2	18	2.38	.141	.21	0.71
room \times signal	1	9	1.65	.231	.15	1.00
order \times signal	2	18	3.35	.083	.27	0.68
method \times signal	1	9	1.54	.246	.15	1.00
room \times order \times method	2	18	3.75	.202	.16	0.87
room \times order \times signal	2	18	0.10	.909	.01	0.97
room \times method \times signal	1	9	0.40	.548	.04	1.00
order \times method \times signal	2	18	0.50	.580	.05	0.84
room \times order \times method \times signal	2	18	0.11	.840	.01	0.73

Table 6: ANOVA for the attribute position.

Effect	df_{num}	df_{den}	F	p	η_p^2	ϵ
room	1	9	9.5	.013	.51	1.00
order	2	18	9.03	.002	.50	0.96
method	1	9	0.01	.939	.00	1.00
signal	1	9	2.90	.123	.24	1.00
room \times order	2	18	2.16	.154	.19	0.84
room \times method	1	9	0.19	.671	.02	1.00
order \times method	2	18	0.20	.760	.02	0.75
room \times signal	1	9	0.61	.456	.06	1.00
order \times signal	2	18	1.37	.276	.13	0.59
method \times signal	1	9	3.78	.084	.30	1.00
room \times order \times method	2	18	0.52	.510	.05	0.60
room \times order \times signal	2	18	0.25	.708	.03	0.71
room \times method \times signal	1	9	0.34	.573	.04	1.00
order \times method \times signal	2	18	0.14	.869	.02	0.98
room \times order \times method \times signal	2	18	0.25	.728	.03	0.77

Table 7: ANOVA for the attribute externalization.

Effect	df_{num}	df_{den}	F	p	η_p^2	ϵ
room	1	9	4.13	.072	.32	1.00
order	2	18	4.16	.044	.32	0.81
method	1	9	0.00	.966	.00	1.00
signal	1	9	2.67	.137	.23	1.00
room \times order	2	18	0.19	.760	.02	0.73
room \times method	1	9	0.25	.627	.03	1.00
order \times method	2	18	1.44	.265	.14	0.68
room \times signal	1	9	1.73	.221	.16	1.00
order \times signal	2	18	0.55	.530	.06	0.68
method \times signal	1	9	3.31	.102	.27	1.00
room \times order \times method	2	18	0.12	.863	.01	0.89
room \times order \times signal	2	18	0.73	.470	.08	0.80
room \times method \times signal	1	9	0.06	.810	.01	1.00
order \times method \times signal	2	18	0.13	.855	.01	0.87
room \times order \times method \times signal	2	18	2.52	.111	.22	0.96

Table 8: ANOVA for the attribute source width.

Effect	df_{num}	df_{den}	F	p	η_p^2	ϵ
room	1	9	4.11	.073	.31	1.00
order	2	18	2.28	.151	.20	0.71
method	1	9	27.80	< .001	.75	1.00
signal	1	9	2.29	.164	.20	1.00
room \times order	2	18	0.74	.44	.08	0.63
room \times method	1	9	0.78	.401	.08	1.00
order \times method	2	18	0.24	.702	.03	0.67
room \times signal	1	9	1.32	.280	.13	1.00
order \times signal	2	18	0.36	.701	.04	0.98
method \times signal	1	9	0.46	.520	.05	1.00
room \times order \times method	2	18	4.71	.030	.34	0.85
room \times order \times signal	2	18	4.03	.043	.31	0.87
room \times method \times signal	1	9	0.00	.971	.00	1.00
order \times method \times signal	2	18	0.14	.856	.02	0.94
room \times order \times method \times signal	2	18	0.25	.760	.03	0.92

Table 9: ANOVA for the attribute envelopment.

Effect	df_{num}	df_{den}	F	p	η_p^2	ϵ
room	1	9	0.42	.530	.04	1.00
order	2	18	7.28	.011	.45	0.74
method	1	9	3.63	.089	.29	1.00
signal	1	9	12.6	.006	.58	1.00
room \times order	2	18	0.53	.513	.05	0.60
room \times method	1	9	0.08	.780	.01	1.00
order \times method	2	18	0.56	.560	.06	0.88
room \times signal	1	9	1.38	.270	.13	1.00
order \times signal	2	18	5.30	.032	.37	0.67
method \times signal	1	9	0.00	1.00	.00	1.00
room \times order \times method	2	18	0.76	.433	.08	0.64
room \times order \times signal	2	18	0.34	.670	.04	0.81
room \times method \times signal	1	9	0.38	.555	.04	1.00
order \times method \times signal	2	18	0.06	.870	.00	0.63
room \times order \times method \times signal	2	18	1.29	.300	.13	0.92